

LEGAL REGULATION OF QUICK-SEARCH ACTIVITY

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Annotation: In the article, the law of the CIS member states, including Ukraine, Kazakhstan, Russia, Kyrgyzstan, Azerbaijan, Lithuania, Armenia, Tajikistan, Moldova, and Belarus "On Rapid Search Activity" and the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Rapid Search Activity" a comparative analysis of the norms of the legislation on prospecting activities were made, and scientifically based proposals were made.

Keywords: rapid-search activities, normative legal documents, international documents.

Legal regulation of search activity refers to laws and regulations regulating relations in search activity.

In this matter, the following was revealed when the norms of the legislation of the CIS member states on the operational search activity were studied. Including, In particular, *Ukraine* In the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Emergency Search Activity", the legal bases of emergency search activity are the Constitution of Ukraine, this law, the criminal, criminal procedural, tax and customs codes of Ukraine, "On the Prosecutor's Office", "On the National Police", "Fighting against corruption" "On the National Bureau of Investigation", "On the State Investigation Bureau", "On the Bureau of Economic Security", "On the State Security Service", "On the State Border Service", "On the State Criminal-Executive Service", "On the State Service of State Body Employees and Officials "On Protection by" Laws and other legal documents, international legal agreements and treaties in which Ukraine is a participant (3-m)¹ In the content of the provision, it is provided that rapid search activities are carried out on the basis of national normative legal documents and international documents.

Republic of Kazakhstan In the law "On emergency search activity": "the legal basis of emergency search activity is the Constitution of the Republic of Kazakhstan, this law and other regulatory legal documents of the Republic of Kazakhstan, if the international agreement ratified by the Republic of Kazakhstan stipulates different rules than those provided for in this law, in which the rules of international agreements are applied, the bodies implementing TQF, in agreement with the Prosecutor General of the Republic, issue normative legal documents regulating the organization and tactics of conducting rapid-search activities based on this law within the scope of their authority (4-m)² From the content of the provision, it should be noted that international legal documents, normative legal documents, including joint decisions made in agreement with the Prosecutor General on the organization and tactics of rapid search activities, serve as a legal basis for the implementation of rapid search activities.

¹ Law of the Republic of Ukraine dated February 18, 1992 No. 2135-XII "On operational-search activity" // Electron manba: <http://online.zakon.kz>. (murojaat vaqti: 03/01/2023).

² Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated September 15, 1994 No. 13 "On operational-search activity" // Electron manba: <https://online.zakon.kz>. (murojaat vaqti: 03/01/2023).

Russian Federation Shining In the law "On emergency search activity": "the legal basis of emergency search activity is the Constitution of the Russian Federation, this law, other laws and other regulatory legal documents of state bodies adopted in accordance with them, the bodies implementing TQF within their powers of the Russian Federation issuing regulatory documents regulating the organization and tactics of rapid-search operations in accordance with the law, the use of special technical tools designed to collect classified information by the Internal Affairs authorities, customs authorities, and the law enforcement service (from surveillance of open spaces, vehicles, and public places) (except) the organization and tactics of the rapid search activities to be determined by the departmental normative legal documents agreed with the Federal Security Service (4-m)"³It was found out that the content is stated in the legal norm, that normative legal documents, which have an open and closed nature, serve as a legal basis for the implementation of operational search activities.

Kyrgyz Republic In the law "On emergency search activity": "the legal basis of emergency search activity is the Constitution of the Kyrgyz Republic, this law, international agreements entered into force in accordance with the procedure established by the legislation of the Kyrgyz Republic, as well as other regulatory documents of the Kyrgyz Republic (paragraph 5)"⁴ The statement of such rules, international documents related to this activity and other normative legal documents indicate that they constitute the legal basis of the operational search activity.

Republic of Azerbaijan In the law "On emergency search activities": "Legislation on emergency search activities consists of other normative legal documents of the Republic of Azerbaijan, as well as international agreements recognized by the Republic of Azerbaijan, and the bodies implementing TQF within their powers, in accordance with the legislation of the Republic of Azerbaijan, adoption of regulatory legal documents regulating the organization and tactics of search operations (2-m)"⁵ As stated in the content, the national regulatory legal documents adopted in the field of operational search activities, international agreements are the legal basis for the organization of operational search activities.

Lithuania Republic Shining In the Law "On Urgent Activities": "Subjects of urgent activities are the Constitution of the Republic of Lithuania, this Law and other laws, international agreements and compliance of the Republic of Lithuania with other legal documents (paragraph 2)"⁶ The presence of provisions in the content determines the normative documents that are applicable in the implementation of the functional obligations of the entities performing their operational activities.

Republic of Armenia In the Law "On Emergency Activities": "Legislative documents on emergency search activities are included in the Constitution of the Republic of Armenia, Criminal Procedure Code, "On the Prosecutor's Office", "On National Security Bodies", "On the Police", "On the Criminal Executive Service" of the Republic of Armenia. ", Laws "On Tax Service", this law and other legal documents, as well as the organization of international

³ Federal Law of the Russian Federation dated August 12, 1995 No. 144-FZ "On operational-search activity" // Electron manba: <http://www.consultant.ru> (murojaat vaqti: 03/01/2023).

⁴ Law of the Kyrgyz Republic dated October 16, 1998 No. 131 "On operational-search activity" // Electron manba:<http://cbd.minjust.gov.kg/> (application time: 01.03.2023).

⁵ Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated October 28, 1999 No. 728-IG "On operational-search activity" // Electron manba:<https://www.legal-tools.org/doc/7871f5/pdf/> (application time: 01.03.2023).

⁶ Law of the Republic of Lithuania dated June 20, 2002 No. IX-965 Vilnius "On Operational Activities" // Electron manba: <https://e-seimas.lrs.lt/> (vakti: 01.03.2023)

agreements recognized by the Republic of Armenia, the process of preparation for operational search activities and their implementation with the regulatory legal documents of the bodies implementing operational search activities. regulation (2-m)"⁷ the existence of provisions in the content of the legal basis of the service activities of the bodies that implement the operational activities of the adopted regulatory legal documents and international documents in this field.

Republic of Tajikistan In the law "On rapid search activities": "The legislation of the Republic of Tajikistan on rapid search activities is based on the Constitution of the Republic of Tajikistan and consists of this law, other normative legal documents of the Republic of Tajikistan, as well as international legal documents recognized by Tajikistan (2-m)"⁸ taking into account the content of the rule, international legal documents, normative legal documents, as stipulated in the laws of Ukraine, Kazakhstan, Russia, Kyrgyzstan, and Lithuania, are the legal basis for the establishment of the TCF.

Republic of Moldova In the law "On special search activity".⁹ it became clear that there is no legal norm on the legal regulation of special search activities.

Belarus Republic In the law "On emergency search activities": "relationships related to the implementation of emergency search activities are regulated by legal documents on emergency search activities, as well as international agreements of the Republic of Belarus, legislation on emergency search activities is based on the Constitution of the Republic of Belarus, this law and that it consists of other legal documents, if the international agreement of the Republic of Belarus stipulates rules different from those stipulated by this law, then the rule of international agreements shall be applied (4-m)"¹⁰ etc., international legal documents and regulatory legal documents are the basis for the implementation of operational search activities.

The Republic of Uzbekistan In the law "On emergency search activities": "the legislation on emergency search activities consists of this law and other legal documents"¹¹ it shows that the rules are established in its content, and how they relate to other legal acts.

Based on the study of the nature of the legal regulation of the operational search activities provided for in the content of the law "On Rapid Search Activities" of the 11 studied countries first of all 9 countries, it is envisaged that international agreements will be the legal basis for the legal regulation of search and rescue activities, and only the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Search and Rescue Activities" does not provide for this provision, and the Law of Moldova TQF contains a norm on the legal regulation of search and rescue activities. that it is not; *secondly*, The fact that the law on TQF of Ukraine, and Armenia clearly states the names of regulatory legal documents regulating operational search activities; *thirdly*, It should be noted that the law on TQF of Kazakhstan, Russia, and Azerbaijan stipulates rules on the

⁷ Law of the Republic of Armenia dated November 19, 2007 No. 3P-223 "On operational-search activity" // Electron manba: <https://e-seimas.lrs.lt/> application time: 03/01/2023).

⁸ Law of the Republic of Tajikistan dated March 25, 2011 No. 687 "On operational-search activity" // Electron manba: <http://www.http://ncz.tj/content> (application time: 28.02.2023).

⁹ Law of the Republic of Moldova dated March 29, 2012 No. 59 "On special investigative activities" // Electron manba: <https://base.spininform.ru> (application time: 03/01/2023).

¹⁰ Law of the Republic of Belarus dated July 15, 2015 No. 307-Z "On operational-investigative activities" // Electron manba: <https://base.spininform.ru/> (application time: 01.03.2023).

¹¹ Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 344 of December 25, 2012 "On Quick Search Activities" // Electronic source: <https://lex.uz/> (application time: 01.03.2023).

adoption of regulatory legal documents regulating the organization and tactics of rapid-search activities of bodies performing rapid-search activities.

Based on the above analysis, Article 2 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Rapid Search Activities" is amended as follows: *The legislation on rapid search activities consists of this Law and other legal documents, as well as international agreements of the Republic of Uzbekistan.*" is suggested to be expressed in the content.

We explain the additions to Article 2 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Quick Search Activities" as follows:

First of all, as it is known, was related to the operational search activity of the normative legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan In the second part of Article 2 of Law No. ORQ-371 of May 14, 2014 "On Prevention of Offenses": "if the international agreement of the Republic of Uzbekistan stipulates different provisions than those stipulated in the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan on crime prevention, the provisions of the international agreement shall be applied." of the Republic of Uzbekistan Considering the Law of August 17, 2020 ORQ-633 "On Combating Human Trafficking", Article 2 of this law states: "If the international agreement of the Republic of Uzbekistan stipulates different rules than those provided for in the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan on combating human trafficking, the rules are defined in the content of the application of the rules of the international agreement, the implementation of legal relations based on international documents in the context of national normative legal documents, as well as the adoption of the Republic of Uzbekistan"Convention for the Suppression of the Traffic in Persons and the Exploitation by Third Parties" (1950) and other international documents related to this field are complied with;

secondly, The seventh paragraph of the first part of Article 15 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Emergency Search Activity" provides "*Questionnaires received on the basis of international agreements of the Republic of Uzbekistan on cooperation in the field of fighting crime and providing legal assistance*", as well as 28¹⁻ indicates that the legal basis for the implementation of rapid search measures in connection with the implementation of the article is established by national normative legal documents and international documents;

thirdly, a total of 115 of which regulate search and rescue activities, according to the classification of international legal documents: 0.9 percent of the declaration; 1.8 percent of the pact; 1.8 percent of the additional statement; 1.7 percent of the agreement; 13, 2 percent of the convention; 32.4 percent of the contract; 48.2 percent of contracts; according to the fields: 4.3 percent are related to ensuring human rights and freedoms; 27.4 percent to organized crime; 12.3 percent to terrorism and extremism; 3.6 percent to the illegal circulation of weapons, ammunition, explosives; 15.7 percent fight against the illegal circulation of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances; 11.3 percent are search, detention and extradition issues; 1.7 percent information security; 16.6 percent provide legal assistance in civil, commercial, family and criminal cases; 3.6 percent to ensure the execution of criminal sentences; Taking into account that 3.5 percent of the relationship is related to rapid search activities in the field of customs, in order to fill the legal gaps in the legislation, we believe that Article 2 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Rapid Search Activities" should be supplemented with the provision "International agreements of the Republic of Uzbekistan".

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